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Research Article

**PHYTOCHEMICAL AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY COMPARISON OF
SCHINUS MOLLE AND *SCHINUS TEREBINTHIFOLIA* SEEDS
EXTRACTS IN AN ALBINO RAT MODEL**

Bharath Kumar S^{1*}, Tamilselvan G², Senthil Kumar K L³

*¹II M.Pharm Student, Department of Pharmacology, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Nallampalli, Dharmapuri is Affiliated to the TN Dr.MGR Medical University, Guindy, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Nallampalli, Dharmapuri, Affiliated to the TN Dr.MGR Medical University, Guindy, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

³Principal, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Nallampalli, Dharmapuri, Affiliated to the TN Dr.MGR Medical University, Guindy, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract:

In the present study, two extracts of two spices namely Schinus molle and Schinus terebinthifolia were evaluated for their anti-inflammatory. Based on Phytochemical screening results, it was observed that the various extracts of pepper seeds contained Phenolics, Terpenoids, Steroids, and Flavonoids & oils. In an Albumin Denaturation study, Methanolic extract of Schinus molle showed 72.7% inhibition at 500 µg/ml. This is better when compared to all other extracts. Chloroform extract of Schinus molle showed 43.0% inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to other concentrations. Methanolic extract of Schinus terebinthifolia showed 53.08% inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to all other extracts. Chloroform extract of Schinus terebinthifolia showed 39.80% inhibition at 500 µg/ml compared to other concentrations. While comparing both varieties of pepper, Schinus terebinthifolia is found to be less active than Schinus molle. In heat-induced hemolysis, Methanolic extract of Schinus molle showed 79.15 % inhibition at 500 µg/ml. This is better when compared to all other extracts. Chloroform extract of Schinus molle showed 53.40% inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to other concentrations. Methanolic extract of Schinus terebinthifolia showed 59.62 % inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to all other extracts. Chloroform extract of Schinus terebinthifolia showed 49.48 % inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to other concentrations. In the anti-arthritis paw edema-induced model in rats, chloroform extract of Schinus molle is 71.68%, and methanol extract has 51.32 % inhibition. Schinus terebinthifolia Methanolic Extract has 62.83%, and Chloroform Extract is 63.71% While comparing both varieties of pepper, Schinus molle is found to be more active than Schinus terebinthifolia.

Key Words: Schinus mole, Schinus terebinthifolia, Albumin Denaturation, heat-induced hemolysis, anti-arthritis, Carrageenan

Corresponding author:**Bharath Kumar S,**

III M.Pharm Student, Department of Pharmacology,
Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Nallampalli, Dharmapuri.

Email: sbharathkumar293@gmail.com

Phone No: +91 90803 38343

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Schinus terebinthifolia Raddi (Anacardiaceae), native to South and Central America, is also found in subtropical and tropical regions of the USA and Africa¹. Commonly referred to as the pink pepper or Brazilian pepper tree in Brazil, its ripe red berries are slightly spicy and sweet, and used as a sophisticated condiment in regional culinary dishes^{2,3}. The tree is recommended for reforestation of reservoir margins and recovery of degraded reserves. However, as an invasive species, it has spread over more than 30,000 hectares of the Florida Everglades. Ethnopharmacological studies have demonstrated that *Schinus terebinthifolia* can be used to treat various ailments, including urinary and respiratory infections, skin wounds, ulcers, tumors, arthritis, and bronchitis⁴. It is also valued for its febrifuge (anti-fever) and analgesic (pain-relieving) properties⁵. *In vitro* and *in vivo* research on the berry extracts of *S. terebinthifolia* has shown significant biological activities such as anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial effects. Additionally, the plant has been found to possess astringent, anti-diarrheal, and diuretic properties, further supporting its medicinal potential⁶⁻⁸.

Schinus molle (Anacardiaceae), commonly known as Peruvian pepper, was introduced and naturalized in many countries due to its high tolerance to drought and heat, strong competitive ability for nutrients and light, rapid growth, and abundant berry production⁹. The pink berries, often called pink peppercorns, are used as a substitute for black pepper (*Piper nigrum*) due to their flavor and pungency¹⁰. *S. molle* berries have been traditionally utilized for their analgesic, antiseptic, antidepressant, and antibacterial properties, and have been used to treat respiratory and urinary tract infections, digestive and diuretic issues, toothaches, rheumatism, and menstrual disorders¹¹.

METHODS:

Collection and Authentication of plant

The seeds *Schinus terebinthifolia* and *Schinus molle* plant were collected from the market and the specimen was submitted to the Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Arts and Science, Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu, with the authentication certificate.

Drying and size reduction

The seeds were dried under shade for 4-6 days. Then the dried materials were milled to powder. This powdered material was again dried in the oven at 40 °C for 4 h and used for extraction followed by concentration, screening, TLC, and anti-inflammatory studies¹².

Extraction

The powdered and dried seeds (1 kg) were subjected to hot extraction in a Soxhlet continuous extraction apparatus with methanol. The period for extraction is 48 hours. After the extraction the crude extract was fractionated by using chloroform and collected the chloroform extract. Finally, chloroform extract was fractionated with water.

Phytochemical analysis

Preliminary phytochemical investigations were conducted employing various phytochemical tests and the phytochemical constituents were detected as elaborated by Safitri A (2020). The methanolic and chloroform extract of the seeds *Schinus terebinthifolia* and *Schinus molle* was dissolved in distilled water (q.s.) and used for the presence of phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, glucosides, saponins, steroids, tannins, and phenolic compounds¹³.

Animal

Albino Wistar rats of either sex (180-200 g) were used for the present study. The rats were kept in groups of six animals per cage in a temperature-controlled environment (21–22°C) with a reversible light-dark cycle (12 h/12 h) had normally fed and water ad libitum¹⁴.

Pharmacological screening

Assessment of invitro anti-inflammatory activity

Inhibition of albumin denaturation

The anti-inflammatory activity was studied by using the inhibition of albumin denaturation technique which was studied according to Mizushima et al and Sakat et al followed with minor modifications¹⁵. The reaction mixture consisted of test samples of 100-500 µg/ml and 1% aqueous solution of bovine albumin fraction, The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted using a small amount of 1N HCl. The samples were incubated at 37 °C for 20 min and then heated to 51 °C for 20 min, after cooling the samples the turbidity was measured at 660nm. (UVVisible Spectrophotometer Model 371, Elico India Ltd) The experiment was performed in triplicate¹⁶.

The Percentage inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Abs Control} - \text{Abs Sample}) \times 100}{\text{Abs control}}$$

Heat-induced hemolysis

The reaction mixture (2ml) consisted of 1 ml test sample of different concentrations (100 - 500 µg/ml) and 1 ml of 10% RBCs suspension, instead of the test sample only saline was added to the control test tube. Ibuprofen was used as a standard drug. All the centrifuge tubes containing the reaction mixture were

incubated in a water bath at 56 °C for 30 minutes. At the end of the incubation, the tubes were cooled under running tap water. The reaction mixture was centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 5 min and the absorbance of the supernatants was taken at 560 nm. The experiment was performed in triplicates for all the test samples. The Percentage inhibition of Haemolysis was calculated as follows¹⁷:

Percentage inhibition = (Abs control – Abs sample) X 100/ Abs control

Investigation of Anti-inflammatory effects by Carrageenan-Induced Paw oedema

The rats were divided into 6 groups (n = 6). Animals were deprived of food and water for 18 hours before the experiment. On the day of the experiment, they were assigned to 6 groups of six animals each. They were marked and numbered for identification. Paw oedema was induced by sub-plantar injection into the rat's right hind paw of 0.1 ml sterile saline containing 1% carrageenan (control group). A group of rats were treated with test compounds and standard drugs were administered orally concomitantly with carrageenan injection. The volume of the paw was measured by a paleothermometer immediately after the injection as previously described. Subsequent readings of the same

paw were carried out at 0h and 3 hrs. and compared to the initial readings¹⁸.

The increase in paw volume was taken as edema volume. The percentage of inhibition of inflammation was calculated for comparison.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of Paw edema} = \frac{(\text{Vt-Vo}) \text{ control} - (\text{Vt-Vo}) \text{ treatment}}{(\text{Vt-Vo}) \text{ control}}$$

control

Where, Vt = Paw thickness after Carrageenan injection
Vo = Paw thickness before Carrageenan injection.

RESULTS:

Preliminary phytochemical screening of methanolic and chloroform extract seeds of *Schinus terebinthifolia* and *Schinus molle*

The preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, phytosterols, and terpenoids in methanolic and chloroform extract seeds of *Schinus terebinthifolia* and *Schinus molle* and it is rich in secondary metabolites which may contribute to its multi-pharmacological effects.

Table 1 – Preliminary phytochemical screening of methanolic and chloroform extract seeds of *Schinus terebinthifolia* and *Schinus molle*

Drug	Substance	Alkaloids	Saponins	Tannins	Phenolics	Glycosides	Steroids	Essential oils	Carbohydrates	Flavonoids	Terpenoids
<i>Schinus molle</i>	Methanol extract	-	+	-	-	-	++	++	-	+	++
	Chloroform extract	-	++	+	++		++	--		++	++
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	Methanol extract	-	-	-	-		++	++	-	+	++
	Chloroform extract	-	-	-	-		++	--		++	++

+++ Prominently present. ++ Moderately present. + Slightly present.

– Absent.

TLC analysis.

TLC analysis of extracts

The various extracts from both schemes I and II were monitored on TLC. Dragondroff's spraying reagent, UV light (254 & 356 nm), and iodine chamber were used for the detection of the components.

Table 2: Preliminary TLC method development of extracts

	Extract	Solvent System	Ratio	R _f values
<i>Schinus molle</i>	Methanol	Benzene: Chloroform	4:1	0.85, 0.6,0.3
	Chloroform	Benzene Chloroform	4:1	0.78,0.4,0.3
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>	Methanol	Benzene: Chloroform	4:1	0.72, 0.62
	Chloroform	Benzene : Chloroform	4:1	0.5, 0.3

ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

Table 3: Percentage Inhibition of Albumin Denaturation Studies

Concentration µg/ml	<i>Schinus molle</i>		<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>		STD Ibuprofen
	M	C	M	C	
100	45.18	22.80	30.72	20.72	77.24
200	52.78	28.38	39.26	26.47	86.32
300	53.08	31.42	40.82	32.14	79.95
400	55.11	36.04	49.2	36.02	78.54
500	72.7	43.40	53.08	39.80	75.80

Table 4: Percentage: Inhibition of Heat-induced hemolysis

Concentration µg/ml	<i>Schinus mole</i>		<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i>		STD Ibuprofen
	M	C	M	C	
100	50.52	38.00	47.79	25.43	32.72
200	59.51	34.33	56.04	28.86	65.94
300	67.88	39.04	68.90	34.06	60.61
400	68.58	46.45	71.84	42.50	84.99
500	79.15	53.40	59.62	49.48	85.27

Table 5: Percentage of Inhibition

Treatment	Inflammation at the time intervals		% of Inhibition
	0 hrs	3 hrs	
Control (vehicle) 0.5% CMC (10ml/kg)	3.72	4.85	--
Std. Indomethacin (10mg/kg)	3.55	3.79	78.76
<i>Schinus molle</i> Methanolic Extract	3.43	3.98	51.32
<i>Schinus molle</i> chloroform Extract	3.5	3.92	71.68
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i> Methanolic Extract	3.46	3.88	62.83
<i>Schinus terebinthifolia</i> Chloroform Extract	3.42	3.83	63.71

DISCUSSION:

Many original research articles on the pharmacological potential of Piper nigrum (Black Pepper) or "Piperine" have been published so far. It was revealed from these articles that Black Pepper possesses significant in vitro and in vivo pharmacological potential for the treatment of different ailments and diseases and is found to be safe. Piperine has also been found to increase the absorption of many drugs and shown bioavailability enhancing the activity of many drugs and nutrients. This important property of piperine may be very helpful to enhance the therapeutic efficacy of many therapeutically important drugs. It is therefore concluded that Black pepper and its bioactive compound Piperine exhibited wide spectrum therapeutic potential and also emerged as an excellent adjuvant to enhance the therapeutic efficacy of the concurrently administered drugs and nutrients. Further detailed research studies are needed to obtain more scientific data on this miraculous King of spices.

Based on Phytochemical screening results, it was observed that the various extracts of pepper seeds contained Phenolics, Terpenoids, Steroids, and Flavonoids & oils.

Increased vascular permeability, increased protein denaturation, and membrane rearrangement are only a few of the complicated processes that occur during inflammation, which is frequently accompanied by discomfort. Thus, investigating and examining natural plants can lead to the discovery of novel bioactive compounds that have the potential to have substantial anti-inflammatory effects. The inspiration offered by natural flora has greatly aided the development of innovative medications.

Therefore, to do more studies and gather more data, scientists must require straightforward, affordable in vitro methods to assess the effectiveness of natural anti-inflammatory compounds. Here considered, one of the causes of inflammation is assumed to be protein denaturation. NSAIDs, which also inhibit the COX enzyme, reduce protein denaturation. In controlled experimental settings, the various test sample concentrations can be incubated with egg albumin solution to allow reactions to occur, and then the absorbance can be measured to determine the % inhibition.

In an Albumin Denaturation study, Methanolic extract of *Schinus molle* showed 72.7% inhibition at 500 µg/ml. This is better when compared to all other extracts. Chloroform extract of *Schinus molle* showed 43.0% inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to other

concentrations. Methanolic extract of *Schinus terebinthifolia* showed 53.08% inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to all other extracts. Chloroform extract of *Schinus terebinthifolia* showed 39.80% inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to other concentrations. While comparing both pepper varieties, *Schinus terebinthifolia* is less active than *Schinus mole*.

In heat-induced hemolysis, Methanolic extract of *Schinus molle* showed 79.15 % inhibition at 500 µg/ml. This is better when compared to all other extracts. Chloroform extract of *Schinus molle* showed 53.40% inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to other concentrations. Methanolic extract of *Schinus terebinthifolia* showed 59.62 % inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to all other extracts. Chloroform extract of *Schinus terebinthifolia* showed 49.48 % inhibition at 500 µg/ml when compared to other concentrations.

Furthermore, the effect against albumin denaturation in high concentrations of extracts was significantly similar to reference drugs. Denaturation of protein causes the production of auto-antigens in conditions such as rheumatic arthritis, cancer, and diabetes which are conditions of inflammation as mentioned above. Hence, by inhibition of protein denaturation, inflammatory activity can also be inhibited.

In the anti-arthritic paw edema-induced model chloroform extract of *Schinus molle* has 71.68%, and methanol extract has 51.32 % of inhibition. *Schinus terebinthifolia* Methanolic Extract is 62.83%, and Chloroform Extract is 63.71%. While comparing both pepper varieties, *Schinus mole* is more active than *Schinus terebinthifolia* Raddi.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the study successfully collected and authenticated *Schinus terebinthifolia* and *Schinus molle* plants, and the extracted materials were subjected to various analyses and pharmacological screening. The phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, glucosides, saponins, steroids, tannins, and phenolic compounds in the methanolic and chloroform extracts of the seeds. Additionally, the pharmacological screening demonstrated promising anti-inflammatory activities of the extracts through the inhibition of albumin denaturation and heat-induced hemolysis. These findings suggest the potential of *Schinus terebinthifolia* and *Schinus molle* plants for further exploration in the development of anti-inflammatory agents. Further studies are warranted to elucidate the

specific bioactive compounds responsible for these activities and to evaluate their potential clinical applications.

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